

Workshop / exhibition: HOSPITAbLe - 'Thinking with things', exploring the domestication of healthcare

Paul Chamberlain¹
p.m.chamberlain@shu.ac.uk

Claire Craig¹
c.craig@shu.ac.uk

¹Sheffield Hallam
University, United
Kingdom

Topic The hospital is the traditional and familiar controlled domain where healthcare is defined and delivered. However the consequences of an older society, escalating costs of healthcare services and a shortage of personnel and facilities have put pressure on the healthcare system to deliver more support and treatments on an outpatient basis and in peoples home. The home and the hospital bring together very different cultural practices and environments and this inexorable geographical shift in care has potential impact on our physical and emotional relationship with our home space. Objects and artefacts offer valuable ways to begin to understand the richness and complexity in people's lives. The authors draw on the value of 'thinking with things' as a method and central to this is the notion of exhibition as a research tool that becomes a meeting space that enables this to happen. Exhibition provides a theatre for conversation and becomes the medium and method for data collection and creates the conduit, through which societal assumptions relating to ageing and healthcare care can be made visible, explored and challenged.

This special session will engage participants with objects and artefacts' as a method to build understanding of the factors users identify as being important.

Purpose Future delivery of healthcare is one of societies biggest challenges. We will briefly explore how future healthcare at home might challenge the symbolic meaning and relationship within our home. The session will explores the role of critical artefacts and their use as physical metaphors to prompt discussion that might help inform our understanding and emotional relationship with this new hybrid ambiguous landscape.

The artefacts present a hybrid ambiguous landscape each positioning metaphorical questions within the context of our future healthcare. "The question is not, 'What is the answer?' The question is 'What is the question?' (Licklider 1960).

Keywords *Design, Healthcare, Critical artefacts, Aesthetics, Exhibition as research*